

Health and Wellbeing Data CoP

ARDC RLA PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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1. PROJECT INFORMATION

PROJECT TITLE AND CODE	RLA Data Community of Practice (CoP) Health and Wellbeing
PROJECT START AND END DATES	May 2024 to 29 Nov 2024
LEAD CONTRACTING ORGANISATION	Research Graph Foundation Ltd
SUBCONTRACTOR REPRESENTATIVE	
PROJECT LEAD CONTACT PERSON	Amir Aryani amir.aryani@researchgraph.org +61405939997
PROJECT MANAGER	Peter Vats peter.vats@researchgraph.org +61409049909
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● University of Canberra Health Research Institution ● Orygen Ltd ● Griffith Regional Insights Data Lab ● Infoxchange Ltd ● Digital Health CRC ● HEAL Network, University of Canberra
FOCUS AREA and ACTIVITY	Research Link Australia: Analysis of research-industry collaboration in the health sector

1.1 Background

As part of Research Link Australia, this project has developed a data-driven approach to enhance the understanding of research-industry collaborations in health and wellbeing. This project includes research institutions, healthcare practitioners, nonprofits, governmental bodies, and private sectors. The objective was to transform fragmented research data into an integrated network, leading to insights into health collaborations. Additionally, this project has augmented this process with domain expert knowledge and provided a platform to synthesise key knowledge on Australia's health and wellbeing collaborative landscape in the public health space.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

The project had the following objectives:

- **Augmented private research information using public RLA graph:** This included creating a cloud-based environment that hosts participants' data in a secure space and transforms their data into an augmented graph.
- **Insights into research-industry collaboration for health and wellbeing:** Achieved as part of the Data CoP workshops by closely working with subject matter experts.
- **Data dashboards from the participants collaboration network:** These dashboards (private and public) animated the data insights derived from Data CoP workshops, and public dashboards contribute to the RLA system.
- **New and enriched funding information:** Integrated research information from the participants tapped into a substantial number of grants from funders such as NHMRC, Medical Research Future Fund (MRFF), NIH (US), Wellcome Trust (UK), and includes philanthropy funding, industry and government contracts such as projects with Public Health Networks (PHNs) and local governments.
- **Develop new data capabilities using RLA data and system:** An organisation level database that enables capabilities, leveraging the RLA system (and data).

1.3 Summary of value

The RLA Data CoP has enabled health and wellbeing organisations to visualise their research collaboration networks. It has provided critical insights into the nature and characteristics of collaborations in the health sector, identifying dynamics that contribute to successful partnerships. This project has highlighted effective strategies for fostering impactful research-industry collaborations, emphasising the qualities of strong partnerships and successful researchers. The insights gained have equipped participants with practical examples of how to use collaboration data to achieve better outcomes.

Looking ahead, the value generated by the RLA Data CoP is expected to grow. By offering a practical demonstration of how the data community of practice workshops can empower researchers, the project has showcased the potential of RLA data to unlock opportunities through networks of industry partners, competitive grants, and collaborative projects with the not-for-profit sector. Additionally, the creation of valuable datasets now accessible to the ARDC RLA platform demonstrates how similar engagements can provide a pathway to synthesis and connect untapped research information.

2. DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1. Achievements against project work packages/deliverables:

Status Key

Completed ▾	Completed
Non Completion may impact on project outc... ▾	Not yet completed and non-completion may have some impact on the project outcomes. Delay has been accepted by the Steering Committee and responsibility for completion has been assigned.
Will not be completed and will impac... ▾	Will not be completed and has an impact on the project outcomes. The Steering committee has accepted the non-completion and understands the impact to the project outcomes.

DELIVERABLE / WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION (INCLUDE LINKS TO RELEVANT DOCUMENTATION)	AGREED DUE DATE	ACTUAL or EXPECTED COMPLETION DATE	STATUS
WP 1 - Augment partners' research information	<p>This work package enabled synthesising and connecting the following research objects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DHCRC collaboration network: 62 projects linked to 117 organisations, 432 researchers, 116 publications Orygen collaboration network: 416 projects/grants linked to 950 organisations, 5,860 publications, 10,718 researchers and participants HRI collaboration network: 196 projects and grants linked to 3,990 organisations, 8,636 researchers, and 2,346 publications HEAL collaboration network: 62 projects and grants linked to 272 organisations, 722 researchers and 102 publications 	15/08/2024	15/08/2024	Comp... ▾

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Infoxchange collaboration network: 114 projects linked to 286 organisations, 350 researchers and 80 publications. ● Griffith collaboration network: 2,353 projects linked to 270 organisations, 2186 researchers <p>In addition, this project augmented this information using RLA data, leading to a large collaboration network that consists of the following research objects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 46,701 projects ● 33,975 organisations ● 337,339 researchers ● 677,870 publications ● 2,539 datasets 			
<p>WP 2 - Data CoP Workshops</p>	<p>This work package provided three in-person workshops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May 2024, Canberra, hosted by the University of Canberra - Sept 2024, Brisbane, hosted by Griffith University - Oct 2024, Melbourne, organised by Orygen Ltd. <p>In these workshops the participants reviewed and discussed data insights presented by 32 data visualisation dashboards. These insights comprised of topics such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Connectivity and characteristics of the partners collaboration network ● Grants/projects research area 	<p>29/11/2024</p>	<p>25/10/2024</p>	<p>Comp... ▾</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National and International Collaboration Networks ● Collaborative Research Projects ● International Grants ● Successful Researchers in Industry Collaboration ● Collaboration Index based on Industry Partners ● Collaboration Index: Researchers (Industry Linked) ● Comprehensive Segmentation and Focus Overview ● Industry/Government Partners ● Research Capabilities <p>These insights were created with the assistance of artificial intelligence applications that utilise large language models for classifying research topics. The results of this work have been presented at the Research Link Australia launch, a Research Data Alliance Plenary Australia Working group and eResearch Australasia 2024 conference.</p>			
WP 3 - Final Report	Publicly accessible report on this project outcomes.	29/11/2024	29/11/2024	Comp... ▾

2.2. Project outputs and outcomes

2.2.1 Outputs

OUTPUTS	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
Open data about research-industry collaboration	This project has led to the creation of a collaboration network, demonstrating the research-industry partnerships in the health and wellbeing sector.	The data and related insights have been presented in the Data CoP workshops. A data integration plan is in place for the RLA system.
Data insights and visualisations	This project has led to the creation of 32 data visualisation dashboards hosted on insights.researchgraph.org	The visualisations have been presented in three workshops, eResearch Australasia Conference and RDA plenary.
Organisation learning and new data capabilities at partner institutions	All partners expressed positive changes in their organisation as the result of implementing this project including <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of data pipelines and processes to connect and synthesise research information. - Identifying missing information in research management systems - Working effectively with researchers and industry partners to complete the missing information. - New reporting capabilities in their organisations, leveraging RLA data combined with their private information. 	This learning has been presented by partners in the Data CoP workshops, documented in minutes, and shared with all partners and ARDC representatives.

2.2.2 Outcomes

OUTCOME	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
<p>New publicly accessible data for RLA community</p>	<p>The data from this project will be publicly accessible using the RLA search portal</p> <p>A separate data publication has been arranged via the Australian Data Archive, in progress at the time of writing this report.</p>	<p>Data integration with the RLA system has been planned and approved by the ARDC RLA team.</p>
<p>Insights into research industry collaboration in the health sector</p>	<p>The work by the Data CoP partners revealed insights into</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Characteristics of collaboration networks in health and wellbeing and their connections with the not-for-profit sector, government and community organisations - The scale and importance of international connections including international funding and industry partnerships - Role of researchers in forming these collaboration networks <p>This work also demonstrated the abundance of untapped data about research-industry collaborations, currently lost in disconnected systems across the sector.</p>	<p>These findings have been presented in the Data CoP workshops, and the workshop presentations are publicly available.</p> <p>An academic publication is in progress that captures and discusses these findings. A pre-print is planned for bioRxiv.</p>

2.3. Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
eResearch presentation	Presentation of the project outcomes at the eResearch Australasia Conference 2024	Approximately 50 attendees in the talk	30 Oct 2024
RDA 23rd Plenary	Data Discovery Interest Group	Approximately 30 attendees in the talk	13 Nov 2024
Workshop 1	University of Canberra, In person event	25 attendees	15 May 2024
Workshop 2	Griffith University, hybrid workshop	9 online, 8 in-person attendees	18 Sept 2024
Workshop 3	Melbourne University, organised by Orygen, in-person event	18 attendees	25 Oct 2024
RLA Launch	Presented as part of the launch of RLA platform	50 attendees	26 Oct 2024
Presentation to Department of Industry, Science and Resources	Presented Data CoP and RLA graph to Strategic Examination of R&D (SERD) group in the department	Approximately 15 attendees including Head of Secretariat Strategic Examination of R&D	10 Oct 2024
Presentation to Cooperative Research Australia	Presenting DHCRC and Data CoP findings	TBA	11 Dec 2024

3. PROJECT IMPACT

3.1. Impact stories

This project has significantly enhanced organisational understanding of the value of information about research-industry collaborations, demonstrating its essential role in driving strategic partnerships. By fostering data capabilities within each participating organisation, the project has empowered teams to leverage collaboration insights more effectively. Additionally, it has established new pipelines and processes to collect and connect collaboration data. The outcome of this project and the journey have set new expectations among executives in partner organisations to improve their understanding and capabilities in leveraging data from Research Link Australia and augmenting their private data.

The following are quotes from our partner organisations:

“Participation in the CoP has helped us recognise that the information we considered largely administrative can indeed help others when captured and shared meaningfully. We have grown an appreciation of how well-structured data we are sitting on can support better linkages, discoverability and opportunities for our partners.”, **Alessandro Luongo, Director of Operations, Digital Health CRC**

“Strategically aligning our research strengths with opportunities has never been more important in our research ecosystem. This tool has the potential to bring to light opportunities for collaboration, innovation and research funding in ways beyond our existing approaches.”, **Vincent Learnihan, Senior Research Specialist, Health Research Institute, University of Canberra**

“The ARDC project has been a major contribution to the Health Research Institute (HRI) for a number of reasons: It coincided with the university review of the HRI and allowed us to present the information with a highly advanced visualisation tool that allowed reviewers and officers at the University of Canberra (UC) to understand better our performance as a research institute, as units within the institute, as specific research programs and also at individual level. The project has allowed us to better understand our strengths and weaknesses or gaps. The use of SNA to represent the information has also allowed us to identify gaps in our database of performance, highlighting the importance of incorporating information on the key databases managed by our centre and related to specific projects. On the other hand the project has illustrated the importance of counting with a register of performance such as PURE, as well as the need to complete the information available from university registers using manual search or other sources. The ARDC project has also allowed us to understand the importance of research

networks as a key information to understand the capability and sustainability of the performance of both individual researchers and research teams or units.” **Prof Luis Salvador-Carulla, Deputy Director of the Health Research Institute, University of Canberra**

“The ARDC project has been highly valuable in supporting the nascent Healthy Environments and Lives (HEAL) National Research Network’s understanding of its broad scope and the extent of its research-policy translation impact. As this is the first time the NHMRC has made such a large investment in research on environmental change and health (\$10M over 5 years), the ARDC project has been timely in helping to further define this field of research.”, **Associate Professor Aditya VYAS, Deputy Director of the Healthy Environments and Lives (HEAL) Global Research Centre**

“We used the data wrangled during the RLA project to produce dashboards for research teams, so they now have access to their own data in a systematic and strategic way, it’s very useful to them for reporting purposes.” **Associate Professor Suzie Lavoie, Orygen Ltd.**

“This is the first time the Not-for-Profit (NFP) sector has been involved in mapping health and wellbeing research collaborations and has shown the enthusiasm of NFPs for building collaborations and capacity for future work. This pilot among NFPs with data capability is a promising start for further exploration among the broader NFP sector” **Dr Kristen Moeller-Saxone, Infoxchange**

3.2. Impact metrics

3.2.1. Use, Outreach and Communications Metrics

ARDC realises that a number of possible impact metrics are lag indicators.

IMPACT METRIC	PROJECT TOTAL TO DATE	DESCRIPTION, LINKS and DOIs
Number of datasets published (preferably with record in Research Data Australia)	TBA	The data publication is currently in the RLA ingestion backlog.
Number of publications citing project or project outputs	TBA	This information is not available yet.
Number of publications that cite /reference the infrastructure or	TBA	This information is not available yet.

service		
Current number of users	32 users	Number of users with current access to the Data CoP insights.
Number of active users (over 90-day period)	56 users	Number of users accessed RLA visualisations and data insights
Number of outreach activities (e.g. seminars, presentations)	7	3 project workshops, 2 conference presentations, 2 government presentations
Social media mentions	3	RLA Launch, eResearch conference and RDA Plenary
Blog posts/news articles that reference infrastructure or service	1	Driving Innovation with Research Link Australia

3.2.2. Links to Publications and Other Communications

Published datasets generated by the platform/infrastructure

DATE	LINK TO A METADATA RECORD OR CITATION WITH DOI
TBA	Data for this project is scheduled for ingestion into the RLA system

Publications using data generated by platform/infrastructure

DATE	CITATION WITH DOI
25 Oct 2024	Relational Insights Data Lab - Griffith University - Presented at RLA Data CoP Workshop 25 Oct 2024, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14241582
25 Oct 2024	Orygen Collaboration Network - Presented at RLA Data CoP Workshop 25 Oct 2024, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14241563
25 Oct 2024	Data Catalyst Network - Presented at RLA Data CoP Workshop 25 Oct 2024, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14239473
25 Oct 2024	Health Research Institute Collaboration Network - Presented at RLA Data CoP

	Workshop 25 Oct 2024, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14241809
25 Oct 2024	HEAL Network - Presented at RLA Data CoP Workshop 25 Oct 2024, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14241860
25 Oct 2024	DHCRC Collaboration Network - Presented at RLA Data CoP Workshop 25 Oct 2024, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14241868
30 Oct 2024	eResearch Conference Presentation: https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/1120-Amir-Aryani.pdf

Blog posts/news articles that reference the platform/infrastructure

DATE	LINK
26 Oct 2024	ARDC post on RLA launch: https://ardc.edu.au/article/driving-innovation-with-research-link-australia/

3.2.3. Details on users of the platform

Data and visualisations produced by the Data CoP have to date been accessible only to project participants and the ARDC team. The following outlines the classification of users who accessed the platform during the project's lifetime.

ORGANISATION TYPE	NUMBER OF USERS
.edu.au	31
.gov.au	3
.org.au	7
.edu	0
.com	10
other	5

4. LESSONS LEARNED

4.1. What Went Well?

The process and outcomes of the RLA Health and Wellbeing Data CoP have been instrumental in revitalising the existing collaborations among project participants and fostering new collaborative pathways. RLA data have proven highly valuable in this process, and across the project partnership, there is significant interest in continuing to use the RLA platform as a supporting system for enhancing institutions' research information.

4.2. What Could be Improved?

The implementation timeline has been a challenge in this project. The Data CoP methodology would benefit from a longer timeframe, allowing for additional workshops and providing better opportunities for community engagement.